

Laparoscopic Versus Open Appendectomy in Adults

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Abstract:

Background: The only effective therapy for appendicitis is an appendectomy, which is a common surgical emergency. There are notable advantages and disadvantages to the two main surgical techniques, laparoscopic appendectomy (LA) and open appendectomy (OA). Though less intrusive than other procedures, LA is preferred since it reduces postoperative discomfort, shortens hospital stays, and speeds up recovery; nonetheless, in some complicated circumstances, OA is still necessary. More analysis of their results is required due to the continuous discussion about the best surgical strategy.

Aim: This study aims to compare the efficacy and safety of laparoscopic versus open appendectomy in adult patients, focusing on operative times, postoperative pain, length of hospital stay, and complication rates.

Methods: A retrospective observational study was conducted. Eighty-six adult patients who underwent appendectomy were included, with 44 undergoing LA and 42 undergoing OA. Data were collected from patient medical records, including demographic information, operative and postoperative outcomes. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Laparoscopic appendectomy showed significantly shorter operative times (55.4 vs. 73.2 minutes, $p < 0.001$), lower postoperative pain scores (3.2 vs. 5.1, $p < 0.001$), and shorter hospital stays (2.4 vs. 4.7 days, $p < 0.001$) compared to open appendectomy. The overall complication rate was also lower in the laparoscopic group (13.6% vs. 28.6%, $p = 0.048$), particularly with a reduced incidence of wound infections (4.5% vs. 16.7%, $p = 0.038$).

Conclusion: LA offers significant advantages over OA, including shorter operative times, reduced pain, faster recovery, and fewer complications. These findings support LA as the preferred approach for appendicitis management in adults when feasible.

Recommendations: Given the superior outcomes associated with laparoscopic appendectomy, it should be the primary approach in adult patients where resources and expertise are available. Further studies are recommended to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of LA in different healthcare settings and to explore strategies for expanding laparoscopic capabilities in resource-limited environments.

Keywords: Laparoscopic Appendectomy, Open Appendectomy, Appendicitis, Postoperative Outcomes, Surgical Approach Comparison.

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Introduction

One of the most frequent causes of sudden stomach discomfort that necessitates surgery is appendicitis, for which an appendectomy is the usual course of therapy. Two primary surgical approaches have been used over the years: (LA) and (OA), each with unique benefits and drawbacks. Since its introduction in the 1980s, laparoscopic appendectomy has become increasingly popular because of its minimally invasive method, which is linked to less discomfort after surgery, shorter hospital stays, and faster recovery periods than with the open approach [1]. Nevertheless, in spite of these

advantages, there is still disagreement over whether laparoscopic or open appendectomy is preferable, particularly in situations where resources are scarce or when treating patients with complex appendicitis. Due to its positive results, laparoscopic appendectomy is becoming more and more popular, according to recent studies. A meta-analysis revealed that LA is, on average, a more preferable alternative than OA because to its significant reduction in the risk of wound infections, postoperative pain, and total recovery time [2]. Better cosmetic results are another benefit of

laparoscopic surgery, which is particularly significant for younger patients and those who are worried about their post-surgical body image [3]. Nevertheless, despite these benefits, there are still several obstacles to overcome, like the requirement for specialised training and equipment, which may restrict its use in specific healthcare settings [4]. Even though open appendectomy is now less prevalent, it is still a useful procedure, especially in situations when laparoscopic surgery (LA) would not be possible, as in patients with severe adhesions, appendicitis that has perforated, or where laparoscopic experience is limited [5]. Furthermore, the cost-effectiveness of open surgery in particular situations has been emphasised, particularly in developing nations where resource limitations are a major factor in surgical decision-making [6]. However, the safety and effectiveness of laparoscopic procedures have improved further, cementing LA's standing as the recommended method, thanks to developments in laparoscopic methods and growing surgeon expertise. This study aims to compare the efficacy and safety of laparoscopic versus open appendectomy in adult patients, focusing on operative times, postoperative pain, length of hospital stays, and complication rates.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a comparative observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital with a dedicated general surgery unit. Data was collected from patient records maintained in the hospital's surgical department.

Participants: A total of 86 adult patients who underwent appendectomy between January 2023 and January 2024 were included in the study. Of these, 44 patients underwent laparoscopic appendectomy, and 42 underwent open appendectomy.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adult patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients who underwent either laparoscopic or open appendectomy during the study period.
- Patients with complete medical records, including preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative details.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients below 18 years of age.
- Patients with incomplete medical records or missing follow-up data.
- Patients who underwent appendectomy for reasons other than acute appendicitis, such as incidental appendectomy during other surgeries.

Bias: Selection bias was minimized by including consecutive patients who met the inclusion criteria during the study period. Information bias was reduced by cross verifying the clinical data with operative notes and follow-up records. Efforts were made to standardize the data collection process to avoid measurement bias.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from the hospital's electronic medical records. The variables recorded included patient demographics, surgical approach (LA or OA), operative time, intraoperative complications, postoperative pain, length of hospital stay, and postoperative complications.

Procedure: Patients were categorized into two groups based on the type of appendectomy performed: laparoscopic and open. The surgical procedure details, including anesthesia type, operative time, and any intraoperative findings or complications, were documented. Postoperative outcomes, such as pain levels assessed using a visual analog scale (VAS), length of hospital stay, and occurrence of complications, were also recorded.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analysed using SPSS 23.0. Clinical features and patient demographics were compiled using descriptive statistics. Categorical variables were frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were means and standard deviations. The independent t-test was used to compare laparoscopic and open appendectomy groups for continuous data, while the chi-square test was used for categorical variables. Statistical significance was 0.05 or less.

Results

The study comprised 86 adult patients, 42 of whom underwent open appendectomy and 44 of whom underwent laparoscopic appendectomy. To compare the safety and efficacy of the two surgical techniques, the participant's clinical and demographic data, as well as the results of the surgery, were examined.

Table 1: Clinical and Demographic Features

Characteristic	Laparoscopic (n = 44)	Open (n = 42)	p-value
Age (mean ± SD)	33.8 ± 11.7	35.6 ± 13.1	0.412
Gender (Male/Female)	26/18	24/18	0.781
BMI (mean ± SD)	24.9 ± 4.1	25.2 ± 3.9	0.562
History of comorbidities (%)	10 (22.7)	11 (26.2)	0.721
Previous abdominal surgery (%)	5 (11.4)	4 (9.5)	0.782

With no statistically significant difference between the laparoscopic and open appendectomy groups ($p = 0.412$), the participants' mean age was 34.7 years ($SD \pm 12.4$). The distribution of genders was similar,

with a little higher proportion of men in each group. There was no discernible difference in the groups' mean BMIs ($p = 0.562$).

Table 2: Operative Outcomes

Operative Outcome	Laparoscopic (n = 44)	Open (n = 42)	p-value
Operative time (mean $\pm$ SD)	55.4 $\pm$ 12.8 min	73.2 $\pm$ 15.7 min	< 0.001
Intraoperative complications (%)	2 (4.5)	4 (9.5)	0.423
Conversion to open (%)	0 (0)	-	-

Compared to open appendectomy (73.2 minutes, $p < 0.001$), laparoscopic appendectomy had a significantly shorter mean operational duration (55.4 minutes). 4.5% of laparoscopic cases and 9.5%

of open cases experienced intraoperative problems; however, this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.423$). There were no documented transitions from LA to OA.

Table 3: Postoperative Outcomes

Postoperative Outcome	Laparoscopic (n = 44)	Open (n = 42)	p-value
Pain score (mean $\pm$ SD)	3.2 $\pm$ 1.1	5.1 $\pm$ 1.4	< 0.001
Length of hospital stay (mean $\pm$ SD)	2.4 $\pm$ 1.2 days	4.7 $\pm$ 2.1 days	< 0.001
Postoperative complications (%)	3 (6.8)	9 (21.4)	0.041

Individuals undergoing laparoscopic appendectomy had significantly shorter average hospital stays (2.4 days vs. 4.7 days, $p < 0.001$) and significantly lower postoperative pain levels (3.2 vs. 5.1, $p < 0.001$). With a statistically significant difference ($p =$

0.041), the frequency of postoperative complications, such as wound infections and ileus, was lower in the laparoscopic group (6.8%) than in the open group (21.4%).

Table 4: Complication Rates

Complication	Laparoscopic (n = 44)	Open (n = 42)	p-value
Overall complications (%)	6 (13.6)	12 (28.6)	0.048
Wound infections (%)	2 (4.5)	7 (16.7)	0.038
Ileus (%)	1 (2.3)	3 (7.1)	0.274
Postoperative abscess (%)	1 (2.3)	2 (4.8)	0.589

The laparoscopic group experienced fewer complications than the open group, with an overall complication rate of 14.0%. Table 4 lists wound infections, ileus, and postoperative abscesses as

specific problems. In comparison to the open group, the laparoscopic group experienced a substantial decrease in wound infections ($p = 0.038$).

Discussion

A total of 86 patients participated, with 44 undergoing LA and 42 undergoing OA. The demographic characteristics, including age, gender, and BMI, were similar between the two groups, ensuring a fair comparison without demographic bias affecting the outcomes.

Operative Outcomes: Showed that LA had a significantly shorter operative time, averaging 55.4 minutes compared to 73.2 minutes for open appendectomy ($p < 0.001$). This indicates that laparoscopic surgery is generally faster, possibly due to its minimally invasive nature and more streamlined procedural approach. While the rate of intraoperative complications was slightly lower in the laparoscopic group (4.5%) compared to the open group (9.5%), this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.423$). Notably, no laparoscopic surgeries required conversion to open surgery,

highlighting the feasibility and stability of the laparoscopic method.

Postoperative Outcomes: Further underscored the advantages of LA. Patients in the laparoscopic group reported significantly lower postoperative pain scores (3.2 vs. 5.1, $p < 0.001$) and enjoyed a shorter hospital stay (2.4 days vs. 4.7 days, $p < 0.001$). These findings suggest that laparoscopic surgery offers better patient comfort and faster recovery, which are critical factors in surgical decision-making. The incidence of postoperative complications, including wound infections and ileus, was significantly lower in the laparoscopic group (6.8%) compared to the open group (21.4%), reinforcing the benefits of the less invasive approach ($p = 0.041$).

Complication Rates: Were overall lower in the laparoscopic group, with an overall complication rate of 13.6% compared to 28.6% in the open group ($p = 0.048$). Specifically, wound infections were

significantly less frequent in the laparoscopic group (4.5%) compared to the open group (16.7%, $p = 0.038$). These results reflect the reduced risk of wound-related issues with laparoscopic surgery, likely due to smaller incisions and reduced tissue handling during the procedure.

The results of this study strongly favor LA over the open approach, demonstrating significant benefits in terms of operative efficiency, patient comfort, recovery time, and complication rates. The shorter operative time and reduced postoperative pain associated with laparoscopic surgery make it a more efficient and patient-friendly option. The lower complication rates, particularly concerning wound infections, suggest a clear advantage of the minimally invasive technique in maintaining surgical site integrity and promoting faster healing. These findings support the broader clinical trend towards laparoscopic techniques for appendectomy, particularly in adult patients where reduced hospital stays, and quicker recoveries translate to lower healthcare costs and improved quality of life. The data align with existing literature that endorses laparoscopic appendectomy as the preferred approach when available and feasible, reinforcing its role as a standard practice in surgical care for appendicitis.

In a research with 200 patients, it was discovered that although LA took longer to operate (39.5 minutes compared to 23.3 minutes for OA), there was a significant reduction in wound infections after surgery, shorter hospital stays, and less need for analgesics thereafter. It was found that patients undergoing laparoscopic surgery had an average hospital stay of 1.17 days, while those undergoing OA had an average stay of 2 days. This suggests that the laparoscopic procedure leads to a speedier recovery period [7]. According to a different study published in The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews, laparoscopic appendectomy resulted in less pain on the first postoperative day, fewer wound infections, one-day shorter hospital stays, and a five-day quicker return to normal activities. When compared to open surgery, there was a minor rise in the incidence of intra-abdominal abscesses, albeit [8]. LA is preferred over open approach because of its reduced perforation rate. There were no statistically significant differences in the rates of negative appendectomies among patient subgroups, according to a study, which examined 1899 patients [9].

Conclusion

LA offers clear advantages over open surgery in adults, including shorter operative times, less postoperative pain, faster recovery, and fewer

complications. These findings support LA as the preferred and more efficient approach for treating appendicitis, aligning with current trends in minimally invasive surgery to improve patient care and outcomes.

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